

An Investigation of the Sacred Landscape of Adinath Temple Complex, Moheshkhali, Cox's Bazar

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Abstract: The sacred landscape of the Adinath Temple is an expression of the heritage and spiritual landscape that has formed over time as a result of the orientation of heritage properties in topographically suitable sites and the influence of harmonious community activities. The Adinath Temple, located on the hill of Moheshkhali Upazila, Cox's Bazar, was built in the 17 century and is one of the oldest examples of religious harmony in Bangladesh. It is inherently a diverse mix of intangible and tangible characteristics that visitors and researchers could not recognize owing to improper maintenance. This study investigates a site in the Adinath Temple Complex, Moheshkhali, with the intent of highlighting the current natural and spiritual context of the religious community by presenting a studied guideline. The objective of this research is to identify the sociocultural significant components that should be preserved, restored, and relocated. The research was conducted in a variety of ways, the most significant being a field survey, a questionnaire survey, the authors' observation, case studies, and data analysis. This study may lead to a heritage management guideline, a potential method for preserving natural and spiritual ecosystems, and a boost to heritage development.

1. Introduction

Sacred landscapes have existed since before the dawn of civilization, and they are locations where we are compelled by the grandeur of nature to ponder the great tales and mysteries of our own origins and to allow ourselves to be fully present for transcendent experiences. (Mann, A. T., and L. Davis. *Sacred landscapes: The threshold between worlds*. New York: Sterling, 2010.) The term "sacred landscape" is used in a broad sense to encompass a wide variety of revered and awe-inspiring places and things (such as part of "spatially dispersed and distinguishable naturally sacred sites," "sacred natural geomorphic features," and communities of "sacred floral and faunal

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species") that are important to the communities in discussion. Consequently, the word incorporates not just spiritually significant sites but also places of symbolic value - those at the intersection of space, place, memory, and spiritual meaning (Jeanrenaud, 2001; Verschuuren, 2007). Extension and geographical limits, and sacred natural physiographical features include a wide array of manifestations that can be contained within spatially dispersed or defined sacred landscapes, such as mountains, oases, valleys, rivers, lakes, caves, forest groves, coastal waters, islands, wetlands, trees, grottoes, and cairns. (Verschuuren, Bas, et al., eds. *Sacred natural sites*. Taylor & Francis, 2012.)

Archaeological enchantment and cultural heritage are regarded as significant for the rebirth of awe, transformation, communal empathy, and the benefit of those to whom they contribute (Perry, Sara. "The enchantment of the archaeological record." *European Journal of Archaeology* 22.3 (2019): 354-371.) According to political theorist Jane Bennett, these sites have the ability to "charm," and in doing so, they serve as incubators for human compassion, ethical awareness, and global concern.

1.1 Heritage and Cultural Values:

The Adinath Temple is one of Bangladesh's holiest pilgrimage sites. It is dedicated to the Hindu god Shiva, also known as Adinath, and is located on the summit of Mainak hill, near to the Moheshkhali channel. Ravana, the cursed king, is said to have left a Shivling at this site. Nur Muhammad Sikder, a wealthy Muslim, discovered the linga and built a temple around the 17th century. A Durga statue was brought from Nepal, and a Durga temple was built next to the Shiva temple. (Baten, M. A. *Moheshkhalir Adinath Mondirer Etikatha*. 2nd ed. Chittagong: Balaka, 2001) On the temple's hill, there is also a Buddhist Jadi.

Mythologically, the Parijat tree is the tree of heaven, and it is found in the temple grounds. Behind the temple are two ponds, one of which is utilized as a holy bath. In addition, there are the Bhairab Temple, the Radha-Govinda Temple, the Shani Temple, and the Advaita-Achuata Dham.

The three faiths have coexisted peacefully (Hindu, Islam, Buddha). Furthermore, several ethnic groups, particularly the Rakhine, pay their respects to the temple. This city commemorates Shiva Chaturdashi with a big extravaganza every year. A fair is held for 10 to 15 days during this time of year.

The authors, of heritage values, noted that the main temple structure was completed in the late 17th century. The architecture of the temple exhibits Islamic influence as well. In 1780, the Buddhist Jadi and other Buddhist monuments were constructed. During the 1971 freedom war, the Pakistani military demolished these structures.

In accordance with traditional practices, the temple is visited three times a day for worship. Here, additional religious ceremonies are also done. Recently, four Hindu temples and one Buddhist temple have sprung nearby, enhancing the site's social significance. There is a small market in the area. Rakhine women also market their traditional attire.

Moheshkhali is an ecological cyclone zone. The temple is approximately 288 meters above sea level. This location is encompassed by hills, swamp forest, and the Moheshkhali Channel.

The Adinath Temple in Moheshkhali has become a landmark for the city. It is now a popular destination for sightseers as well as religious pilgrims. However, the temple is losing its former splendor due to a lack of conservation work.

The study aims to investigate and identify the cultural and heritage values of the sacred landscape with spatial and cultural mapping and build a framework to conserve and reserve the elements with a proper heritage management. Cultural mapping is a powerful tool for communities to be able to recognize, trace, and locate their cultural treasures. Social behaviors, traditions, tales, knowledge, beliefs, etc. that are significant to communities and that locate people in their places, in the world, can be collected using cultural mapping to generate a narrative about a place's identity. (Cabeça, Sónia Moreira. "Cultural mapping: A sustainable methodology for intangible cultural heritage." *Memoriamedia Review* 3 (2018): 1-9.)

This study aims at highlighting the potential of cultural mapping to contribute to the long-term impact of the built environment, with a special emphasis on the role of spatial and intangible mapping: community-held and -maintained intangible cultural heritage (UNESCO, 2013) is a cultural resource that should be leveraged for the benefit of areas and their people.

2. Assessment and Mapping Methodology

2.1 Sample Selection

The research area is located in Thakurthala, a village in the Choto Moheshkhali union. The boundary of Moheshkhali upazila is 9km west-north from Cox's Bazar district headquarters. The site's uppermost portion is at the contour level. Moheshkhali is the only island in Bangladesh with hills. Approximately 2 kilometers at the west there is an Upazila Parishad. Cox's Bazar contains boats that can be utilized for transportation. It is also accessible via road from Chakaria.

Figure 1: Site and Surroundings -Google Map
(Developed by Authors.)

From survey; On the eastern side of the property, there are swamp trees and the Moheshkhali Channel. There are hills on the site's western side. The steep region dominates the northern half of the property. There are Hindu temples, a Buddhist temple, a slaughterhouse, and a paddy field on the southern side of the property. Moheshkhali Island is south of Cox's Bazar in Bangladesh. There are mosques, temples, and pagodas. Adinath Temple in Moheshkhali is a pilgrimage must-see. The Hindu literature states the temple was built a thousand years earlier than historical records indicate. Moheshkhali people claim a Muslim built the temple. (Bangladesh National Portal, n.d. Moheshkhali Upazila)

This temple is spiritual, archaeological, and historical. It's an ancient Hindu temple with rare resources like the Amaranth flower and Twin Pond. The Hindu god Shiva has always been worshipped. The approximately 288-foot-high twin pond has never stopped flowing.

2.2 Methodological Phases

The qualitative research methodology included participant and non-participant observation as well as loosely structured focus-group interviews. The communication language was a blend of Bangla and Arakan. Pantha Sharma conducted the fieldwork.

Cultural mapping is an effective tool for governance because it gives concrete form to intangibles by enlisting the participation of locals in a bottom-up effort to define their community's character and the unique qualities that make it stand out from others. Numerous cultural mapping initiatives have been carried out in various parts of the world, providing rich fodder for this project's methodological development. Ian Cook and Ken Taylor present a fascinating comparative analysis of numerous cultural mapping case studies (Cook and Taylor 2013). Drawing from the existing literature on cultural mapping, the following methodological stages have been chosen for performing the study project (figure 2):

Figure 2: 5 Steps Method Applied for this Research. (Developed by Authors.)

The research utilized both qualitative and quantitative methods. Utilizing field surveys, questionnaires, author observation, case studies, current approaches of conservation, cultural assessment value and data analysis, the research was conducted. There are numerous precedent cases of cultural assessment value and spatial mapping projects from throughout the world focused on conservation, which provides a solid foundation for the development of this project's methodology.

2.2 Materials and Sample Size

The investigation is analytical in scope. The study used a convenient sampling strategy. One hundred people were polled for this study; 60 men and 40 women. The poll was carried out in 2020 during the months of January and March and September and October. A questionnaire with limited space for free-form responses was created. Visitors' evaluations of the Adinath temple in Moheshkhali (the Dependent Variable) were employed in a regression study of the identifying

areas' (the Unbiased Variables Accommodation, Accessibility, Attraction, Amenities, and Activity).

2.3 Experimental procedure

Knowing the historical value of a property is essential before making any decisions about its future. This leads to choices that are future-proof since they are consistent with these ideals. Criteria for evaluation are essential for deciding which cultural assets should be prioritized for investigation and inclusion (Affairs 2001).

Figure 3: Experimental Procedure developed by Authors.

2.4 Questionnaire formulation and administration

Several factors are chosen to comprehend the stimulation and overall experience of visiting the Adinath temple in Maheshkhali. For more insight into what motivates visitors to come, we look at demographic data, pilgrims' gut instincts, and actual cultural and religious activity. The quality of the cultural experience is ultimately determined by examining factors such as accommodation, ease of access, amenities, attractions, activities and the conservation of heritage values in places.

3. Value Assessment of the Study Area

Figure 4: Value Assessment (developed by Authors)

3.1 Tangible Value (on-site)

In Tangible values, there are Adinath Shrine (Temple of Lord Shiva), Durga Shrine (Temple of eight-armed Goddess Durga). Secondary Shrines: Bhairab shrine, Radha Govinda Shrine, and Shani shrine, Adavaita-Ashuta Dham, Parijat flowers, two ponds, Tomb: There are some tombs in front of the main shrine, And Buddhist Jadi.

3.2 Intangible Value (on-site)

There are significant intangible values, such as, Moheshkhali Channel, Swamp Forest: There is a man-made Swamp Forest to protect from cyclones. Adinath Jetty., Hills, Religious landscape (4 Hindu temples and 1 Buddhist temple growing there) and Slaughter-place.

3.3 Tangible Value (Site around)

Legends and Mythological stories, Buddhist Jadi., Celebrations and rituals, Ethnic values.

The value assessment demonstrates that the Adinath temple is significant not only from an archaeological and historical standpoint but also from a religious one. The preservation of the place and its illustrious past might be helped along in the appropriate direction by first determining the heritage values that should be preserved there.

4. Result and Discussions

The architectural interpretation of "Chakra" is proposed to connect all the heritage values in the study area. Shiva is the god of yoga. Yoga enables ascension to Shiva or Paramatma, as well as joy. Chakras (wheel and circle) are conventional tools for meditation. Seven Chakras are Muladhara, Svadhisthana, Manipura, Anahata, Vishuddha, Ajna, and Sahasrara. Chakras depict body components. Chakras energize spiritual emotions and functions. Ascending from the lower chakras to the crown chakra, the yogi internalizes spiritual elevation.

Figure 5: Zoning

Figure 6: Framework

The notion guides design selections. The basic zoning is arranged around the seven chakras. This journey begins at the marketplace and ends at the observation space. There are also essential auxiliary functions.

5. Conclusion

The research has the potential to recognize the site's many attributes and values. In the development process, the lack of functions required by the social, religious, and cultural context is a fundamental concern. This study investigates the socio-cultural and heritage values of Adinath Temple, as well as its preservation and regeneration characteristics. This may be attainable through the development of a sustainable community with a well-planned landscape. This research technique prepares the basis for future initiatives that are compatible with both contemporary and ancient traditions. The findings of this study may assist individuals in comprehending the necessity of preserving cultural and traditional values alongside modern progress. This research also aids in the comprehension of the evolution pattern of the spiritual environment.

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